

On Grounding Extensions in Abstract Argumentation

Extended version with all proofs

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Abstract. The grounded semantics is the baseline semantics for abstract argumentation frameworks as it constitutes the most skeptical outcome of the argumentation. Based on the observation that, for many other semantical notions, any extension can be reduced to the grounded extension of a sub-framework, we investigate conceptual and complexity-theoretic questions on how this *grounding* of extensions behaves. In particular, we identify how minimal sets of attacks (also called *critical attacks*) can be disregarded to obtain a simple representation of possible complex extensions, and provide a full characterisation of computational complexity for six popular semantics. Our approach can particularly be used to explain the inner structure of complex extensions.

1. Introduction

Abstract argumentation frameworks [1] are approaches for modelling argumentative scenarios that represent arguments as nodes in a directed graph, where a directed edge represents an attack from one argument to another. Reasoning in abstract argumentation frameworks consists of identifying sets of arguments (*extensions*) that form a *plausible* outcome of the argumentation. Several different semantical approaches for formalising plausibility in this context have been proposed, see e. g. [1,2]. Central to most of these approaches are the concepts of *conflict-freeness* and *admissibility*, which model the requirements that a plausible outcome should be free of internal conflicts and defend itself against threats from the outside, respectively. Many different semantics have been proposed based on these notions, but also based on different concepts such as rankings [3], weights [4], or probabilities [5].

In this work, the grounded semantics [1] is of special interest. The grounded extension of an abstract argumentation framework is uniquely determined and can be easily defined using a very simple procedure. More precisely, the grounded extension is obtained by first accepting all arguments that are unattacked (i. e., that have no incoming edge), then removing them and all arguments attacked by them, and iterating this pro-

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cedure until no further arguments can be accepted. Using this procedure, the acceptability of arguments in the grounded extension is also easily explained, as there is no cyclic dependency between accepted arguments and acceptability of an argument follows naturally from the acceptability of its defenders. The grounded extension can be regarded as the most skeptical (or cautious) outcome of the modelled argumentation. In fact, any extension of most other semantics, in particular complete, preferred, stable, and semi-stable semantics [2], has the grounded extension as a subset. Moreover, it can also easily be seen (see Proposition 2 below), that by removing some attacks of the abstract argumentation framework, any extension of the above-mentioned semantics (and also many more) can be recovered as the grounded extension of the resulting smaller framework. This insight is central for the work presented in this paper. It allows us to reduce a possibly complex (in terms of defense structure) extension to a more simple structure that is easily explainable. Moreover, removed attacks can be regarded as *inactive* attacks, also called *critical attacks* in [6], that do not change the validity of the original extension.

In this paper, we analyse the above setting from a conceptual and complexity-theoretic point of view. In particular, we introduce σ -critical sets of attacks that, when removed from the framework, yields that the grounded extension of the resulting framework is a σ -extension of the original framework. We analyse this notion for complete, preferred, stable, and semi-stable semantics and also consider the measure of *grounding distance*, which for a certain σ -extension is the minimal size of a corresponding σ -critical set. As the main contribution, we characterise the computational complexity of certain decision problems in this context. This analysis also shows some interesting differences in the relationships between semantics. While for most settings [7], the complexity of problems for stable and preferred semantics usually differ by one level on the polynomial hierarchy (e. g., for deciding skeptical acceptance), here we observe that deciding on an upper bound for the *grounding distance*, we only differ between the classes NP (for stable semantics) and DP (for preferred semantics).

In summary, the contributions of this paper are as follows.

1. We introduce σ -critical sets of attacks and analyse their properties (Section 3).
2. We introduce *grounding distance* as a quantitative tool and analyse its properties (Section 4).
3. We provide a full complexity characterisation of certain problems in our setting (Section 5).

Moreover, Section 2 recalls necessary preliminaries, Section 6 discusses some related works, and Section 7 concludes.

2. Abstract argumentation

An *abstract argumentation framework* F is a tuple $F = (A, R)$ where A is a (finite) set of arguments and R is a relation $R \subseteq A \times A$ [1]. For two arguments $a, b \in A$ the relation aRb means that argument a attacks argument b . For a set $S \subseteq A$ we define

$$S_F^+ = \{a \in A \mid \exists b \in S, bRa\} \quad S_F^- = \{a \in A \mid \exists b \in S, aRb\}$$

If S is a singleton set, i. e., $S = \{a\}$ for some $a \in A$, then we also just write a_F^+ (resp. a_F^-) for $\{a\}_F^+$ (resp. $\{a\}_F^-$).

We say that a set $S \subseteq A$ is *conflict-free* if for all $a, b \in S$ it is not the case that aRb . A set S *defends* an argument $b \in A$ if for all a with aRb there is $c \in S$ with cRa . A conflict-free set S is called *admissible* if S defends all $a \in S$.

Different semantics [2] can be phrased by imposing certain constraints on sets of arguments. In particular, a set S

- is a *complete* (co) extension iff it is admissible and for all $a \in A$, if S defends a then $a \in S$,
- is a *grounded* (gr) extension iff it is complete and minimal,
- is a *stable* (st) extension iff it is conflict-free and $S \cup S_F^+ = A$,
- is a *preferred* (pr) extension iff it is admissible and maximal.
- is a *semi-stable* (sst) extension iff it is complete and $S \cup S_F^+$ is maximal.

All statements on minimality/maximality are meant to be with respect to set inclusion. For a semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{co, gr, st, pr, sst}\}$ let $\sigma(F)$ denote the set of all σ -extensions of $F = (A, R)$. Since the grounded extension is uniquely determined [1], we directly write $\text{gr}(F) = S$ for the grounded extension of F (instead of $\text{gr}(F) = \{S\}$).

For some proofs, it will be convenient to use the following characterisation of the grounded extension, which relies on the notion of the *reduct* [8]. For a framework $F = (A, R)$ and $S \subseteq A$, the *reduct* F^S of F wrt. S is $F^S = (A', R')$ with $A' = A \setminus (S \cup S_F^+)$ and $R' = R \cap (A' \times A')$. Let furthermore $\text{unatt}(F) = \{a \mid a_F^- = \emptyset\}$ be the set of unattacked arguments of F .

Proposition 1. *Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework with $n = |A|$. We have*

$$\text{gr}(F) = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$$

where $S_1 = \text{unatt}(F)$ and $S_i = \text{unatt}(F^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$ for all $i = 2, \dots, n$.

In other words, the grounded extension $\text{gr}(F)$ of F can be determined by iteratively adding all unattacked arguments and removing all those arguments and those attacked by them. Note that this characterisation is merely a notational variant of the definition of the grounded extension via the *characteristic function* [1] and is therefore given without proof.

For $A' \subseteq A$ define the *projection* $F|_{A'}$ of F to A' as $F|_{A'} = (A', R \cap (A' \times A'))$. We are also interested in so-called *local deletions* [9], i. e., sub-frameworks of F that are obtained by removing certain attacks. For $R' \subseteq A \times A$ define

$$F - R' = (A, R \setminus R').$$

We also call $F - R'$ the *restriction* of F by R' .

3. Grounding extensions through σ -critical attacks

The central motivation for our work is given by the following observation.

Proposition 2. *Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework and $\sigma \in \{\text{co, gr, st, pr, sst}\}$. If $S \in \sigma(F)$ then there is $R' \subseteq R$ such that $S = \text{gr}(F - R')$.*

Figure 1. The argumentation framework F_1 from Example 1.

Figure 2. The argumentation framework F_2 from Example 2.

Proof. Define

$$R' = \{(a, b) \in R \mid b \in S\}.$$

Then every argument in S is unattacked in $F - R'$ and therefore $S \subseteq \text{gr}(F - R')$. Assume $S \neq \text{gr}(F - R')$, then there is an argument $c \in \text{gr}(F - R')$ with $c \notin S$, $S \cup \{c\}$ is conflict-free in $F - R'$, and S defends c in $F - R'$. Assume $S \cup \{c\}$ is not conflict-free in F , so there is a $b \in S$ and $(b, c) \in R$ or $(c, b) \in R$:

- Case $(b, c) \in R$: this directly violates the conflict-freeness of $S \cup \{c\}$ in $F - R'$ as $(b, c) \notin R'$.
- Case $(c, b) \in R$: Since $S \in \sigma(F)$, S is admissible in F and must defend b , so there is $b' \in S$ with $(b', c) \in R$. But as $b' \in S$ and the attack (b', c) is also present in $F - R'$, the set $S \cup \{c\}$ would not be conflict-free in $F - R'$.

So $S \cup \{c\}$ is conflict-free in F . As S defends c in $F - R'$, it also defends c in F . So S is not complete in F , contradicting $S \in \sigma(F)$ since $\sigma(F) \subseteq \text{co}(F)$ for all $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$. It follows $S = \text{gr}(F - R')$. \square

In other words, any extension $S \in \sigma(F)$ can be defined as the grounded extension of a certain restriction $F - R'$ of F . However, note that there may be multiple R' for which this statement may be true (see also below).

We illustrate the observation from Proposition 2 with some examples.

Example 1. We consider the abstract argumentation framework F_1 in Figure 1, with $\sigma(F_1) = \{\{b, d\}, \{b, e\}, \{a, c, e\}\}$ for $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{st}, \text{sst}\}$. We take $S = \{b, d\}$ and let $R' = \{(c, b), (e, d)\}$. The restriction $F_1 - R'$ is depicted in Figure 1, if attacks indicated in gray and a dashed line are disregarded. It is then easy to see that $\text{gr}(F_1 - R') = S$.

Example 2. Examine the abstract argumentation framework F_2 in Figure 2. We consider $S = \{c, e, g\}$ with $S \in \sigma(F_2)$ and $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$. Let $R' = \{(a, c), (d, c), (d, e), (f, g), (h, g), (h, e)\}$. The restriction $F_2 - R'$ is also shown in Figure 2, with the attacks in R' indicated in gray and a dashed line. We then have that $\text{gr}(F_2 - R') = S$.

Observe that the other direction of the statement in Proposition 2 (i. e., from $S = \text{gr}(F - R')$ for some R' it follows that $S \in \sigma(F)$) is not true in general (consider removing all attacks). Following [6], we call sets R' for which the statement holds σ -critical.

Definition 1. Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework and $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$. A set $R' \subseteq R$ is σ -critical for F if $\text{gr}(F - R') \in \sigma(F)$.

In other words, a set of attacks R' is σ -critical if the grounded extension of $F - R'$ is a σ -extension of F . If $S = \text{gr}(F - R')$ for $S \in \sigma(F)$ we also say that S is grounded by R' .

Example 3. We consider again the abstract argumentation framework F_1 in Figure 1. We have that $R' = \{(c, b), (e, d)\}$ is σ -critical for F_1 and $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$. Note that $R'' = \{(c, b), (e, d), (b, c)\}$ is also σ -critical with $\text{gr}(F_1 - R'') = \{b, d\}$. Similarly, even $R''' = \{(e, d)\}$ is σ -critical for F_1 and the same semantics.

We identify some simple properties of critical attacks that are used later.

Proposition 3. Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework, $R' \subseteq R$, and $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$.

1. \emptyset is gr-critical and co-critical for F .
2. If $\sigma(F) \subseteq \sigma'(F)$ and R' is σ -critical then R' is σ' -critical.
3. for $\sigma \neq \text{co}$, \emptyset is σ -critical in F iff $\sigma(F) = \text{gr}(F)$.

Proof.

1. We have $\text{gr}(F - \emptyset) = \text{gr}(F)$ and since the grounded extension is complete we also have $\text{gr}(F - \emptyset) = \text{gr}(F) \in \text{co}(F)$.
2. From $\text{gr}(F - R') \in \sigma(F)$ and $\sigma(F) \subseteq \sigma'(F)$ it directly follows $\text{gr}(F - R') \in \sigma'(F)$.
3. If \emptyset is σ -critical in F then $\text{gr}(F) \in \sigma(F)$. Since all semantics in $\{\text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$ satisfy *I-maximality*² [10] and each extension of these semantics contains the grounded extension, it follows that $\text{gr}(F)$ is the only σ -extension, so $\sigma(F) = \text{gr}(F)$. The other direction follows from item 1. \square

As illustrated in Example 3 there may be multiple sets R' and R'' such that R' and R'' are both σ -critical and we also have $\text{gr}(F - R') = \text{gr}(F - R'')$. Naturally, we are interested in minimal modifications of F in order to obtain a grounding of a certain extension $S \in \sigma(F)$.

Definition 2. Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework and $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$. A set $R' \subseteq R$ is *minimally* σ -critical for F , if R' is σ -critical for F and for all R'' with $R'' \subsetneq R' \subseteq R$, R'' is not σ -critical for F .

In the above definition, we consider minimality in terms of subset minimality, which appears to be the most natural choice to us. However, in the next section we will also consider the case of minimality wrt. cardinality.

Example 4. We continue Example 3 with the abstract argumentation framework F_1 in Figure 1. We have that $R''' = \{(e, d)\}$ is minimally σ -critical for F_1 and $\sigma \in \{\text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$. The other minimally σ -critical sets for F_1 are $R' = \{(b, c), (d, e)\}$ and $R'' = \{(c, b), (d, e)\}$, where we obtain $\text{gr}(F_1 - R') = \{a, c, e\}$ and $\text{gr}(F_1 - R'') = \{b, e\}$, respectively. On the other hand, \emptyset is the only minimally σ' -critical set for $\sigma' \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}\}$.

²A semantics σ satisfies *I-maximality* iff for all $F = (A, R)$ and $S, S' \in \sigma(F)$, if $S \subseteq S'$ then $S = S'$.

We can observe that attacks in a minimal σ -critical set are necessarily attacks onto the extension under consideration.

Proposition 4. *Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework and $\sigma \in \{\text{co, gr, pr, st, sst}\}$. If R' is minimal σ -critical and $S = \text{gr}(F - R')$, then for all $(a, b) \in R'$ we have $a \in S_F^- \cap S_F^+$ and $b \in S$.*

Proof. Let R' be minimally σ -critical, $S = \text{gr}(F - R')$, $(a, b) \in R'$ and $R'' = R' \setminus \{(a, b)\}$. Assume first that $b \notin S$. Consider $F - R''$ and we show that R'' is σ -critical, i. e., we have that $S = \text{gr}(F - R'')$. Suppose that S is not conflict-free in $F - R''$. Then, S would not be conflict-free in F , since we only removed attacks. Suppose that S does not defend itself in $F - R''$. Then, S would not defend itself in $F - R'$, where only the attack (a, b) is removed. It follows that S is admissible in $F - R''$. Now recall that the grounded extension is the maximal (wrt. set inclusion) strongly admissible set [2], so S is strongly admissible in $F - R'$. We also have that S is strongly admissible in $F - R''$: for every $x \in S$ there is $S' \subseteq S \setminus \{x\}$ that is strongly admissible and defends x (these are the same sets S' as for $F - R'$ since no attacks on S have been added going from $F - R'$ to $F - R''$). It follows $S \subseteq \text{gr}(F - R'')$.

Assume $S \neq \text{gr}(F - R'')$, so there is $c \notin S$ such that S defends c in $F - R''$. If $c = b$ then S also defends c in $F - R'$ (since $F - R'$ does not contain the attack (a, b)), contradicting $S = \text{gr}(F - R'')$. It follows $c \neq b$. Since S does not defend c in F (otherwise S would not be complete), there must be $(d, c) \in R$ with no $e \in S$ and $(e, d) \in R$. Since S defends c in $F - R''$ it follows $(d, c) \in R''$ and therefore $(d, c) \in R'$ (otherwise c cannot be defended by S in $F - R''$). This contradicts the minimality of R' as c is also not defended by S in $F - (R' \setminus \{(d, c)\})$ and we have $S = \text{gr}(F - (R' \setminus \{(d, c)\}))$. It follows $b \in S$.

From that, $a \in S_F^-$ follows by definition. Note that in case $a \in S$, we have that S is not conflict-free, which contradicts $S \in \sigma(F)$. Assume now that $a \notin S_F^+$. Then, we have aRb , but S does not defend b against a in F , which contradicts the fact that $S \in \sigma(F)$. It follows that $a \in S_F^- \cap S_F^+$. \square

In other words, every attack in a σ -critical set is an attack on the extension that is also defended against by the extension.

Example 5. We continue Example 4 with the abstract argumentation framework F_1 in Figure 1. If we consider any of the minimally pr-critical sets for F_1 , we notice that every attack is either between b and c or d and e . More specifically, if, for instance, the attack (d, e) is included in the minimally pr-critical set, then the argument e is contained in the resulting grounded extension. The same holds for all other attacks in minimally pr-critical sets.

The following results dive a bit deeper into the inner structure of σ -critical sets. In particular, we show that (except for complete semantics) subsets of σ -critical sets that are also σ -critical always ground the same extension (Lemma 1). Moreover, the lattice over the subset relation of σ -critical sets is *smooth*, i. e., any set ‘between’ two σ -critical sets is also σ -critical (see Lemma 2). This allows us to obtain a simple characterisation (Proposition 5) of σ -critical sets that will be useful later for our complexity analysis.

Lemma 1. *Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework, $R' \subseteq R'' \subseteq R$, and $\sigma \in \{\text{pr, st, sst, gr}\}$. If R' and R'' are σ -critical then $\text{gr}(F - R') = \text{gr}(F - R'')$.*

Figure 3. The argumentation framework F_3 from Example 6.

Proof. First observe that the statement is trivially satisfied for $\sigma = \text{gr}$ since the grounded extension is uniquely determined and we have $\text{gr}(F - R') = \text{gr}(F) = \text{gr}(F - R'')$.

Let $n = |A|$ and

$$\text{gr}(F - R') = S'_1 \cup \dots \cup S'_n$$

$$\text{gr}(F - R'') = S''_1 \cup \dots \cup S''_n$$

as in Proposition 1. Assume $\text{gr}(F - R') \neq \text{gr}(F - R'')$. Since σ satisfies I-Maximality [10], we have neither $\text{gr}(F - R') \subsetneq \text{gr}(F - R'')$ nor $\text{gr}(F - R') \supsetneq \text{gr}(F - R'')$, so we have in particular $\text{gr}(F - R') \setminus \text{gr}(F - R'') \neq \emptyset$. Let $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ be the smallest index such that there is $a \in S'_i$ but $a \notin \text{gr}(F - R'')$. Consider the following cases:

1. Assume there is $b \in \text{gr}(F - R'')$ with $(b, a) \in R \setminus R''$. Since $(b, a) \in R \setminus R''$ we also have $(b, a) \in R \setminus R'$ (due to $R' \subseteq R''$). As $a \in S'_i$, a is unattacked in $(F - R')^{S'_1 \cup \dots \cup S'_{i-1}}$. If $i = 1$ then necessarily $a \in S'_1$ as well (a is also unattacked in $F - R''$ and therefore $a \in \text{gr}(F - R'')$), so we have $i > 1$. Then there must be a $c \in S'_{i-1}$ with $(c, b) \in R \setminus R'$ and therefore $(c, b) \in R$. Since $\text{gr}(F - R'')$ is conflict-free, it follows $c \notin \text{gr}(F - R'')$. This is a contradiction to the assumption that i is the smallest index such that there is $a \in S'_i$ but $a \notin \text{gr}(F - R'')$ (since $c \in S'_{i-1}$ and $c \notin \text{gr}(F - R'')$).
2. Assume there is no $b \in \text{gr}(F - R'')$ with $(b, a) \in R \setminus R''$. Since i is the smallest index such that there is $a \in S'_i$ but $a \notin \text{gr}(F - R'')$ we have

$$S'_1 \cup \dots \cup S'_{i-1} \subseteq \text{gr}(F - R'')$$

Since $a \in S'_i$, a is unattacked in $(F - R')^{S'_1 \cup \dots \cup S'_{i-1}}$. As $(F - R'')$ has even less attacks than $(F - R')$, a is also unattacked in $(F - R')^{\text{gr}(F - R'')}$ and $\text{gr}(F - R'') \cup \{a\}$ is conflict-free. So $\text{gr}(F - R'')$ cannot be grounded and we arrived at a contradiction.

It follows $\text{gr}(F - R') = \text{gr}(F - R'')$. □

Note that the above statement can be generalised to any semantics that satisfies I-Maximality [10]. However, observe that the above statement is not satisfied for the complete semantics (which also does not satisfy I-Maximality).

Example 6. We consider the abstract argumentation framework F_3 in Figure 3. We have that $\text{co}(F_3) = \{\{a\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}\}$. Consider, for instance, $R' = \emptyset$ and $R'' = \{(b, c), (d, c)\}$, which are both co-critical for F_3 and we have $R' \subseteq R''$. However, it is easy to see that $\text{gr}(F_3 - R') = \{a\} \neq \{a, c\} = \text{gr}(F_3 - R'')$. In contrast to that, R' is not σ -critical for F_3 with $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{st}, \text{sst}\}$ while R'' is not gr-critical for F_3 .

Lemma 2. Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework, $R' \subseteq R''' \subseteq R'' \subseteq R$, and $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{st}, \text{sst}, \text{gr}\}$. If R' and R'' are σ -critical then R''' is σ -critical.

Proof. Let $n = |A|$ and

$$\text{gr}(F - R') = S'_1 \cup \dots \cup S'_n$$

$$\text{gr}(F - R'') = S''_1 \cup \dots \cup S''_n$$

$$\text{gr}(F - R''') = S'''_1 \cup \dots \cup S'''_n$$

as in Proposition 1.

As R' and R'' are σ -critical we have $\text{gr}(F - R') = \text{gr}(F - R'')$ due to Lemma 1. We show $\text{gr}(F - R''') = \text{gr}(F - R')$, which directly implies that R''' is σ -critical. Assume $\text{gr}(F - R''') \neq \text{gr}(F - R'')$ and assume $\text{gr}(F - R''') \setminus \text{gr}(F - R'') \neq \emptyset$ (the other case is analogous). Let $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ be the smallest index such that there is $a \in S'''_i$ but $a \notin \text{gr}(F - R'')$. So a is unattacked in $(F - R''')^{S'''_1 \cup \dots \cup S'''_{i-1}}$. Since $(F - R'')$ has even less attacks than $(F - R''')$, a is also unattacked in $(F - R'')^{S''_1 \cup \dots \cup S''_{i-1}}$. As i is the smallest index with $a \in S'''_i$ but $a \notin \text{gr}(F - R'')$, we have $S'''_1 \cup \dots \cup S'''_{i-1} \subseteq \text{gr}(F - R'')$ and we have that a is unattacked in $(F - R'')^{\text{gr}(F - R'')}$, contradicting the fact that $\text{gr}(F - R'')$ is grounded. \square

From Lemma 1 and Lemma 2 we can derive the following characterisation for minimal σ -critical sets, which basically says that imposing minimality computationally only adds polynomial overhead.

Proposition 5. *Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework, $R' \subseteq R$, and $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{st}, \text{sst}, \text{gr}\}$. The following two statements are equivalent:*

1. R' is minimally σ -critical.
2. R' is σ -critical and for all $(a, b) \in R'$, $R' \setminus \{(a, b)\}$ is not σ -critical.

Proof. The direction (1) \Rightarrow (2) follows directly by definition. The direction (2) \Rightarrow (1) follows from Lemma 2. For that to see, assume R' is σ -critical and for all $(a, b) \in R'$, $R' \setminus \{(a, b)\}$ is not σ -critical. If R' would not be minimally σ -critical, then there is $R'' \subseteq R'$ and R'' is σ -critical. Then necessarily $R'' \subseteq R' \setminus \{(a, b)\} \subseteq R'$ for some $(a, b) \in R'$ and by Lemma 2 $R' \setminus \{(a, b)\}$ must be σ -critical, contradicting the assumption. \square

The notion of (minimal) σ -critical sets allows us to explain the acceptability of arguments in an arbitrary extension in a procedural manner. More precisely, if R' is minimally σ -critical and grounds $S \in \sigma(F)$, then we can first set aside the attacks R' and explain why $S = \text{gr}(F - R')$ by following the characterisation of Proposition 1: some arguments of S are unattacked, they are accepted right away. Then arguments attacked by already accepted arguments can be safely removed since they are defeated. We iterate this procedure until no more arguments can be accepted. Then we attend again the attacks in R' and see (thanks to Proposition 4) that these are attacks from arguments defeated through the previous process and thus of no consequence to the acceptability of the arguments in S .

Example 7. We consider again the abstract argumentation framework F_2 in Figure 4 and the preferred extension $S = \{c, e, g\}$. We examine the minimally pr-critical set $R' = \{(a, c), (d, e), (h, g), (f, g)\}$ (again indicated in gray), which allows us to explain the acceptability of S as follows. Initially, only the argument g is unattacked. After removing

Figure 4. The argumentation framework F_2 and the restriction $F_2 - R'$ from Example 7.

the defeated argument h , the argument e is now unattacked and can be accepted. Finally, due to the removal of the defeated argument d , the argument c can be accepted, and no further arguments may be accepted.

Alternatively, the set $R'' = \{(a, c), (d, e), (h, g), (h, e)\}$ is also minimally pr-critical for S in F_2 . Under this critical set, we first accept e and, after the removal of d and f , can accept both c and g in the second step.

4. Grounding distance

The notion of σ -critical sets allows us also to *measure* the effort required for grounding extensions quantitatively.

Definition 3. Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework, $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$, and $S \in \sigma(F)$. The *grounding distance* $\text{gdist}_F^\sigma(S)$ of S in F wrt. σ is defined as

$$\text{gdist}_F^\sigma(S) = \min\{|R'| \mid R' \text{ is } \sigma\text{-critical for } F \text{ and } S = \text{gr}(F - R')\}$$

with $\min \emptyset = \infty$.

In other words, $\text{gdist}_F^\sigma(S)$ is the minimal size of σ -critical set that grounds S (here now in terms of set cardinality). It therefore captures how close S is to being grounded and can therefore be used as a measure of the inner complexity (in terms of defense structure) of S .

Example 8. We continue Example 4 with the abstract argumentation framework F_1 in Figure 1 and consider $\sigma \in \{\text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$. For the σ -extension $S = \{b, d\}$, we have $\text{gdist}_F^\sigma(S) = 1$. On the other hand, we also have $\text{gdist}_F^\sigma(\{b, e\}) = \text{gdist}_F^\sigma(\{a, c, e\}) = 2$. Finally, for the grounded extension $\text{gr}(F_1) = \emptyset$, we obtain $\text{gdist}_F^{\text{gr}}(\emptyset) = 0$. Note that for any other set $S' \subseteq A$, we get a grounding distance of ∞ .

Some simple observations on the grounding distance are as follows.

Proposition 6. Let $F = (A, R)$ be an abstract argumentation framework, $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$, and $S \in \sigma(F)$.

1. $\text{gdist}_F^\sigma(S) \neq \infty$ iff $S \in \sigma(F)$.
2. $\text{gdist}_F^{\text{gr}}(\text{gr}(F)) = 0$.

Proof.

1. If $\text{gdist}_F^\sigma(S) \neq \infty$ then let $R' \subseteq R$ be such that $|R'| = \text{gdist}_F^\sigma(S)$ and R' is σ -critical for F and $S = \text{gr}(F - R')$. Since R' is σ -critical it follows that $S \in \sigma(F)$. The other direction follows from Proposition 2.
2. From Proposition 3 (1) we know that \emptyset is gr-critical, therefore $\text{gdist}_F^{\text{gr}}(\text{gr}(F)) = 0$. \square

The grounding distance can be used to compare different σ -extensions and it allows finer-grained reasoning by considering only those σ -extensions with ‘small’ grounding distance. In particular, this measure can be used as a selection criterion for the approach of [11], which uses such selection criteria to filter out some σ -extensions and defines a variant of skeptical reasoning taking only the remaining σ -extensions into account, see also [12] for a similar work in this direction. We leave a deeper investigation of this aspect for future work.

5. Computational complexity and algorithms

We assume familiarity with basic concepts of computational complexity and basic complexity classes such as P, NP, coNP, see [13] for an introduction. The prototypical NP-complete problem is SAT (=satisfiability) which asks whether a given propositional formula Φ (usually given in *conjunctive normal form*, CNF) is satisfiable. The prototypical coNP-complete problem is UNSAT (=unsatisfiability) which asks whether a given propositional formula Φ is unsatisfiable.

For two complexity classes \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} , the class $\mathcal{C}^{\mathcal{D}}$ is the class of decision problems solvable by an algorithm in class \mathcal{C} that has access to an *oracle* of class \mathcal{D} (which means that the algorithm can obtain the answer of any problem in class \mathcal{D} within one step). The class $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ is the class of decision problems solvable by a deterministic polynomial-time algorithm that can make polynomially many *parallel* (or *non-adaptive*) calls to an NP-oracle (so results of the calls cannot influence the problems solved by other calls). Note that $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}} = \text{P}^{\text{NP}[\log]}$, where $\text{P}^{\text{NP}[\log]}$ is the class of decision problems solvable by a deterministic polynomial-time algorithm that can make only logarithmically many calls to an NP-oracle, but which can be *adaptive* (i. e., the result of one oracle call can influence the problem definition for the next oracle call). Finally, we require knowledge of the class DP, which is defined via $\text{DP} = \{L_1 \cap L_2 \mid L_1 \in \text{NP}, L_2 \in \text{coNP}\}$. In other words, DP is the class of problems that are intersections of NP and coNP problems (but note that, under standard complexity-theoretic assumptions, $\text{DP} \neq \text{NP} \cap \text{coNP}$). The prototypical DP-complete problem is SAT-UNSAT (=unsatisfiability) which asks whether for a given pair (Φ, Ψ) of propositional formulas, it is true that Φ is satisfiable and Ψ is unsatisfiable.

We consider the following computational tasks:

VERCRITICAL $_{\sigma}$	Input: $F = (A, R), R' \subseteq R$ Output: YES iff R' is σ -critical
VERMINCRITICAL $_{\sigma}$	Input: $F = (A, R), R' \subseteq R$ Output: YES iff R' is minimally σ -critical
DISTUPPER $_{\sigma}$	Input: $F = (A, R), S \subseteq A, k \in \mathbb{N}$ Output: YES iff $\text{gdist}_F^\sigma(S) \leq k$

σ	$\text{VERCRITICAL}_\sigma$	$\text{VERMINCRITICAL}_\sigma$	DISTUPPER_σ
co	in P	trivial	NP-c
gr	in P	trivial	in P
st	in P	in P	NP-c
pr	coNP-c	coNP-c	DP-c
sst	coNP-c	coNP-c	DP-c

Table 1. Computational complexities of the problems $\text{VERCRITICAL}_\sigma$, $\text{VERMINCRITICAL}_\sigma$, and DISTUPPER_σ for $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$.

Informally, the problem VERCRITICAL is about verifying whether a given set of attacks is σ -critical, wrt. some given semantics σ . Similarly, the problem VERMINCRITICAL is about verifying whether a given set of attacks is minimally σ -critical. The problem DISTUPPER is about checking whether some given integer k is an upper bound for the grounding distance of a given set of arguments S .

In order to characterise the complexity of some of the above problems, the following (quite straightforward) observation will be helpful.

Lemma 3. *Let F be an abstract argumentation framework. Deciding whether $\sigma(F) = \text{gr}(F)$ is coNP-complete for $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$.*

Proof. Let S_{gr} be the grounded extension of F . Recall that $S_{gr} \subseteq S$ for every $S \in \text{pr}(F)$ and $S \in \text{sst}(F)$, we have therefore $\text{pr}(F) = \text{gr}(F)$ iff S_{gr} is preferred and $\text{sst}(F) = \text{gr}(F)$ iff S_{gr} is semi-stable. So for coNP-membership, we have to decide whether S_{gr} is preferred resp. semi-stable, which are both coNP-complete, cf. [7].

For hardness, we consider a variant of a reduction from UNSAT by [14], see also the discussion in [7]. The decision problem UNSAT asks for a given propositional formula Φ in CNF whether Φ is unsatisfiable. Let $\Phi = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ with clauses C_1, \dots, C_n over atoms x_1, \dots, x_m . Define $F_\Phi = (A_\Phi, R_\Phi)$ via

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_\Phi &= \{\Phi, \bar{\Phi}, C_1, \dots, C_n, x_1, \bar{x}_1, \dots, x_m, \bar{x}_m\} \\
 R_\Phi &= \{(\Phi, \bar{\Phi}), (\bar{\Phi}, \Phi), (C_1, \Phi), \dots, (C_n, \Phi)\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{(C_1, C_1), \dots, (C_n, C_n)\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{(\bar{\Phi}, x_1), (\bar{\Phi}, \bar{x}_1), \dots, (\bar{\Phi}, x_m), (\bar{\Phi}, \bar{x}_m)\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{(x_1, \bar{x}_1), (\bar{x}_1, x_1), \dots, (x_m, \bar{x}_m), (\bar{x}_m, x_m)\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{(\dot{x}_i, C_j) \mid \dot{x}_i \in \{x_i, \bar{x}_i\}, \dot{x}_i \in C_j\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5 shows an example of the construction. As it has been shown elsewhere [14, 7], Φ is unsatisfiable if and only if \emptyset is a preferred extension of F_Φ (resp. semi-stable extension). Since \emptyset is also the grounded extension of F_Φ , Φ is unsatisfiable if and only if $\text{pr}(F_\Phi) = \text{gr}(F_\Phi)$ (resp. $\text{sst}(F_\Phi) = \text{gr}(F_\Phi)$). Since UNSAT is coNP-hard, we also have that deciding whether $\sigma(F) = \text{gr}(F)$ is coNP-hard for $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$, completing the proof. \square

We can now provide a complete complexity characterisation of the above problems.

Figure 5. The abstract argumentation graph F_Φ for $\Phi = \{\{x_1, x_3\}, \{\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_3\}, \{\bar{x}_2, x_4\}\}$.

Theorem 1. Let $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{pr}, \text{sst}\}$. The computational complexities for the problems $\text{VERCRITICAL}_\sigma$, $\text{VERMINCRITICAL}_\sigma$, and DISTUPPER_σ are as shown in Table 1.

Proof.

1. $\text{VERCRITICAL}_{\text{co}}$ is in P:

We can compute the grounded extension of $F - R'$ and verify whether it is a complete extension of F in polynomial time, cf. [7].

2. $\text{VERMINCRITICAL}_{\text{co}}$ is trivial:

Since \emptyset is co-critical (as the grounded extension is complete), R' is minimally co-critical iff $R' = \emptyset$.

3. $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{co}}$ is NP-complete:

For membership, consider the following algorithm on input (F, S, k) :

- (a) Guess a set $R' \subseteq R$
- (b) If R' is co-critical, $S = \text{gr}(F - R')$, and $|R'| \leq k$, return YES
- (c) Otherwise return NO

The above algorithm runs in non-deterministic polynomial time and solves $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{co}}$, so $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{co}}$ is in NP.

For hardness, we reduce from SAT and use a variant of the standard reduction, cf. the proof of Lemma 3. On input $\Phi = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ over atoms x_1, \dots, x_m we construct a framework $F'_\Phi = (A'_\Phi, R'_\Phi)$ defined via

Figure 6. The abstract argumentation graph F'_Φ for $\Phi = \{\{x_1, x_3\}, \{\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_3\}, \{x_2, x_4\}\}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A'_\Phi &= \{\Phi, \bar{\Phi}, x_1, \bar{x}_1, \dots, x_m, \bar{x}_m\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{C_1, \dots, C_n, D_1, \dots, D_m\} \\
 R'_\Phi &= \{(\Phi, \bar{\Phi}), (\bar{\Phi}, \Phi), (C_1, \Phi), \dots, (C_n, \Phi)\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{(C_1, C_1), \dots, (C_n, C_n)\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{(D_1, \Phi), \dots, (D_m, \Phi)\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{(D_1, D_1), \dots, (D_m, D_m)\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{(\bar{\Phi}, x_1), (\bar{\Phi}, \bar{x}_1), \dots, (\bar{\Phi}, x_m), (\bar{\Phi}, \bar{x}_m)\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{(\hat{x}_i, C_j) \mid \hat{x}_i \in \{x_i, \bar{x}_i\}, \hat{x}_i \in C_j\} \\
 &\quad \{(x_1, D_1), (\bar{x}_1, D_1), \dots, (x_m, D_m), (\bar{x}_m, D_m)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 6 shows an example of the construction. Observe that in contrast to the construction from Figure 5, there are no mutual attacks between the arguments representing complementary variables. Note that the arguments D_1, \dots, D_m represent additional clauses of the form $\{x_i, \bar{x}_i\}$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$, which do not change the satisfiability of Φ since these are always satisfied. It should be clear that

$$E_0 = \{x_1, \bar{x}_1, \dots, x_m, \bar{x}_m, \Phi\}$$

is a complete extension (and the only non-empty complete extension) of F'_Φ , independently of Φ . We show now that Φ is satisfiable if and only if $\text{gdist}_{F'_\Phi}^{\text{co}}(E_0) \leq m$.

- “ \Rightarrow ”: Let Φ be satisfiable and $\omega : \{x_1, \dots, x_m\} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$ be a model of Φ . Define

$$\begin{aligned}
 R'' &= \{(\bar{\Phi}, x_i) \mid \omega(x_i) = \text{true}, i = 1, \dots, m\} \cup \\
 &\quad \{(\bar{\Phi}, \bar{x}_i) \mid \omega(x_i) = \text{false}, i = 1, \dots, m\} \\
 &\subseteq R'_\Phi
 \end{aligned}$$

Then R'' is co-critical as $\text{gr}(F'_\Phi - R'') = E_0$:

- * First $\text{gr}(F'_\Phi - R'') \subseteq E_0$ should be clear since all other arguments attack themselves
- * Each x_i with $\omega(x_i) = \text{true}$ is unattacked in $F'_\Phi - R''$ and therefore contained in the grounded extension, analogously for all \bar{x}_i with $\omega(x_i) = \text{false}$.
- * Each C_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) is attacked by at least one of the above, since ω is a model and each clause is satisfied (so one argument above attacks it)
- * Each D_j ($j = 1, \dots, m$) is attacked, since exactly one of each pair x_i, \bar{x}_i is accepted above.
- * Since all C_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$) and D_j ($j = 1, \dots, m$) are attacked, Φ is accepted.
- * Since Φ is accepted, all remaining x_i and \bar{x}_i are defended against $\bar{\Phi}$.

This shows $\text{gr}(F'_\Phi - R'') = E_0$ and that R'' is co-critical and since $|R''| = m$ we have shown $\text{gdist}_{F'_\Phi}^{\text{co}}(E_0) \leq m$.

- “ \Leftarrow ”: Assume $\text{gdist}_{F'_\Phi}^{\text{co}}(E_0) \leq m$ and let $R'' \subseteq R'_\Phi$ with $|R''| \leq m$ be co-critical. We assume that

$$R'' \subseteq \{(\bar{\Phi}, x_1), (\bar{\Phi}, \bar{x}_1), \dots, (\bar{\Phi}, x_m), (\bar{\Phi}, \bar{x}_m)\} \quad (1)$$

This can be assumed due to the following observations:

- * If $(C_i, \Phi) \in R''$ for some $i = 1, \dots, n$, we could remove (C_i, Φ) from R'' and add $(\bar{\Phi}, \dot{x}_j)$ for an arbitrary $\dot{x}_j \in C_i$. Then \dot{x}_j would be unattacked and defeat C_i , rendering the attack (C_i, Φ) ineffective after all (and we did not change the cardinality of R'').
- * The same reasoning as above applies for any $(D_i, \Phi) \in R''$
- * $(\Phi, \bar{\Phi}) \notin R''$ as all x_i, \bar{x}_i would be undefended.
- * It should also be clear that R'' contains none of the self-attacks (or they could be removed from R'' without changing criticality, since all self-attacking arguments are defeated anyways)
- * Also, R'' does not contain any attack of the form (\dot{x}_i, C_j) (or they could be removed from R'' without changing criticality)

So we have (1). Now observe that there cannot be any $i = 1, \dots, m$ such that neither $(\bar{\Phi}, x_i) \in R''$ nor $(\bar{\Phi}, \bar{x}_i) \in R''$, as in that case $\bar{\Phi}$ would not be defended from D_i . It follows that $|R''| = m$ and R'' contains exactly one of each pair $(\bar{\Phi}, x_i), (\bar{\Phi}, \bar{x}_i)$ for all $i = 1, \dots, m$. Define now an interpretation $\omega : \{x_1, \dots, x_m\} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$ via $\omega(x_i) = \text{true}$ iff $(\bar{\Phi}, x_i) \in R''$. Since $\text{gr}(F''_\Phi - R'') = E_0$ and $\bar{\Phi} \in E_0$, the argument $\bar{\Phi}$ is defended against all C_1, \dots, C_n in E_0 . This means for each C_i , there is $\dot{x}_i \in C_i$ that is unattacked in $F''_\Phi - R''$. It follows that C_i is satisfied by ω . So ω is a model of $\bar{\Phi}$, showing that $\bar{\Phi}$ is satisfiable.

4. $\text{VERCRITICAL}_{\text{gr}}$ is in P:

We can compute the unique grounded extensions $\text{gr}(F)$ and $\text{gr}(F - R')$ and check $\text{gr}(F) = \text{gr}(F - R')$ all in polynomial time.

5. $\text{VERMINCRITICAL}_{\text{gr}}$ is trivial:

Since \emptyset is gr-critical (Proposition 3), R' is minimally gr-critical iff $R' = \emptyset$.

6. $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{gr}}$ is in P:

Consider the following deterministic polynomial-time algorithm for solving $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{gr}}$ (on input $F = (A, R), S \subseteq A, k \in \mathbb{N}$):

- (a) Determine $S' = \text{gr}(F)$
- (b) If $S \neq S'$ return NO
- (c) Return YES

Observe that the above algorithm is correct since $\text{gdist}_F^{\text{gr}}(\text{gr}(F)) = 0$ (see Proposition 6) and $\text{gdist}_F^{\text{gr}}(S) = \infty$ for all $S \neq \text{gr}(F)$.

7. $\text{VERCRITICAL}_{\text{st}}$ is in P:

We can compute the grounded extension of $F - R'$ and verify whether it is a stable extension of F in polynomial time, cf. [7].

8. $\text{VERMINCRITICAL}_{\text{st}}$ is in P:

This follows directly from Proposition 5 and that fact that $\text{VERCRITICAL}_{\text{st}}$ is in P (see above).

9. $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{st}}$ is NP-complete:

The proof is completely analogous to the proof for $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{co}}$. In particular, observe that in the construction F''_{Φ}, E_0 is also stable.

10. $\text{VERCRITICAL}_{\text{pr}}$ is coNP-complete:

For membership, we consider the complement problem $\text{COVERCRITICAL}_{\text{pr}}$, which asks whether R' is *not* pr-critical wrt. $F = (A, R)$ and show that it is in NP via the following algorithm:

- (a) Let $S = \text{gr}(F - R')$
- (b) If S is not admissible in F return YES
- (c) Guess $S' \subseteq A$
- (d) If S' is admissible and $S \subsetneq S'$ return YES
- (e) Return NO

Observe that the above algorithm returns YES if either the grounded extension of $F - R'$ is not admissible in F or there is an admissible superset of it in F . In both cases $\text{gr}(F - R')$ cannot be preferred in F . It follows $\text{VERCRITICAL}_{\text{pr}} \in \text{coNP}$. Hardness follows directly from Lemma 3 and item 3 of Proposition 3 (which shows that already deciding whether \emptyset is pr-critical is coNP-hard).

11. $\text{VERMINCRITICAL}_{\text{pr}}$ is coNP-complete:

For membership, we consider the complement problem $\text{COVERMINCRITICAL}_{\text{pr}}$, which asks whether given R' is *not* minimally pr-critical wrt. $F = (A, R)$. Consider the following non-deterministic algorithm:

- (a) If $\text{gr}(F - R')$ is not admissible in F , return YES
- (b) Guess S with $\text{gr}(F - R') \subsetneq S$
- (c) If S is admissible, return YES
- (d) Guess $R'' \subsetneq R'$
- (e) If $\text{gr}(F - R'')$ is admissible in F , return YES
- (f) Return NO

Observe that the above algorithm covers all reasons why R' is not minimally pr-critical: at (a) we show that R' is not pr-critical as it does not yield an admissible set. At (b)-(c) we consider that $\text{gr}(F - R')$ is admissible but that there is an admissible superset S (so $\text{gr}(F - R')$ is not preferred). At (d)-(e), we show that R' is not minimal, as R'' also yields an admissible set in F , which is either equal to $\text{gr}(F - R')$ or a superset of it; in both cases R' is not minimally pr-critical.

The algorithm runs in polynomial time showing that $\text{COVERMINCRITICAL}_{\text{pr}}$ is in NP. It follows that $\text{VERMINCRITICAL}_{\text{pr}}$ is in coNP.

Hardness follows from the fact that $\text{VERCRITICAL}_{\text{pr}}$ is already coNP-hard.

12. $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{pr}}$ is DP-complete:

For DP-membership, observe that $\text{gdist}_F^{\text{pr}}(S) \leq k$ if and only if the following two conditions are met (let $F = (A, R)$):

- (a) S is a preferred extension of F .
- (b) There is $R' \subseteq R$ with $|R'| \leq k$ and $\text{gr}(F - R') = S$.

Problem (1) is in coNP and problem (2) is in NP, so $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{pr}}$ is in DP.

For hardness, we consider a reduction from the problem of deciding whether for a pair (Φ, Ψ) of formulas in CNF it is the case that Φ is satisfiable and Ψ is unsatisfiable, which is a DP-complete problem. Without loss of generality, we assume that Φ and Ψ have disjoint signatures, i. e., let Φ be defined over x_1, \dots, x_m and let Ψ be defined over $y_1, \dots, y_{m'}$. We combine reductions from the proof of Lemma 3 and from the proof of item 3. above. For an instance (Φ, Ψ) define $F_{\Phi, \Psi} = (A_{\Phi, \Psi}, R_{\Phi, \Psi})$ via

$$\begin{aligned} A_{\Phi, \Psi} &= A'_\Phi \cup A_\Psi \\ R_{\Phi, \Psi} &= R'_\Phi \cup R_\Psi \end{aligned}$$

Observe that $F_{\Phi, \Psi}$ consists of two disjoint subgraphs, one as in Figure 6 for Φ and one as in Figure 5 for Ψ . Let (as in item 3. above) E_0 be defined as

$$E_0 = \{x_1, \bar{x}_1, \dots, x_m, \bar{x}_m, \Phi\}$$

We claim that Φ is satisfiable and Ψ is unsatisfiable if and only if $\text{gdist}_{F_{\Phi, \Psi}}^{\text{pr}}(E_0) \leq m$.

- “ \Rightarrow ”: Let Φ be satisfiable and Ψ be unsatisfiable. Then E_0 is a stable extension of F'_Φ and \emptyset is the only preferred extension of F_Φ . It follows that $E_0 \cup \emptyset = E_0$ is a preferred extension of $F_{\Phi, \Psi}$. As in the proof of item 3. above, a model of Φ can be translated into a set $R'' \subseteq R'_\Phi$ with $|R''| = m$ such that $\text{gr}(F'_\Phi - R'') = E_0$. It also holds $\text{gr}(F_{\Phi, \Psi} - R'') = E_0$ and therefore $\text{gdist}_{F_{\Phi, \Psi}}^{\text{pr}}(E_0) \leq m$.
- “ \Leftarrow ”: Assume $\text{gdist}_{F_{\Phi, \Psi}}^{\text{pr}}(E_0) \leq m$ and let $R'' \subseteq R_{\Phi, \Psi}$ with $|R''| \leq m$ such that $\text{gr}(F_{\Phi, \Psi} - R'') = E_0$. It should be clear that R'' cannot contain attacks from R_Ψ , since this has no influence on E_0 . Then as in the proof of item 3. above, we can infer that $|R''| = m$ and R'' contains exactly one of each pair $(\Phi, x_i), (\Phi, \bar{x}_i)$ for all $i = 1, \dots, m$. It follows that Φ is satisfiable. Moreover, since E_0 is a preferred extension, the uniquely defined preferred extension of the subgraph F_Ψ must be \emptyset (otherwise E_0 would not be maximal). This means that Ψ is unsatisfiable.

This shows DP-hardness.

13. $\text{VERCRITICAL}_{\text{sst}}$ is coNP-complete:

Analogous to the coNP-completeness proof of $\text{VERCRITICAL}_{\text{pr}}$ above.

14. $\text{VERMINCRITICAL}_{\text{sst}}$ is coNP-complete:

Analogous to the coNP-completeness proof of $\text{VERMINCRITICAL}_{\text{pr}}$ above.

15. $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{sst}}$ is DP-complete:

The proof is completely analogous to the proof for $\text{DISTUPPER}_{\text{pr}}$. In particular, note that the sets of preferred and semi-stable extensions coincide in $F_{\Phi, \Psi}$.

□

6. Related works

The notion of *critical attacks* has been introduced in [6], which, first and foremost, analyses this notion from a conceptual point of view and its relationships to concepts from game theory. In particular, [6] considers the *Skeptic's argumentation game*, which is an application of *win-move* programs for solving two-player games to abstract argumentation frameworks. The solution of these programs is equivalent to the grounded extension and [6] identifies (among other things) critical attacks as relevant for finding the *provenance* of certain choices made during the game. However, their investigation does not touch those aspects we considered in this paper, in particular, they did not conduct an analysis of computational complexity.

Also related to our work is the area of *extension enforcement* [9], in particular for grounded semantics [15,16]. The computational problem addressed here is given an argumentation framework $F = (A, R)$ and a set $S \subseteq A$, how to minimally ‘change’ F to F' such that S is an extension of F' . While the literature on enforcement considers a wide variety on different change operations, our setting fits the scenario of grounded extension enforcement under local deletions [9]. However, there are certain noteworthy differences to our setting. First, we only consider enforcement of sets S that are already σ -extensions (so our scenario always considers two semantics: σ and the grounded semantics). Moreover, we are more interested in the critical sets and their role in ‘grounding extensions’. This has direct influence on our computational complexity analysis, which is completely orthogonal to the computational complexity of grounded enforcement [15].

Another related field are explanations in formal argumentation. Various works are concerned with the problem of explaining the acceptance [17,18,19] or rejection of individual arguments [20,21,22]. For instance, in [23] sufficient and necessary reasons for the acceptance or rejection of arguments are considered. Complementary to that, there are also approaches that consider explaining sets of arguments [24,25,26]. Related to that, in [27] a scheme for recursively constructing extensions along the strongly connected components (SCCs) of an argumentation framework is introduced. In [28], this idea is then used to construct structural explanations for acceptance in probabilistic argumentation frameworks by constructing σ -extensions according to the SCC-structure. Notably, the above mentioned works are usually focused on the arguments in the argumentation framework, while we are more interested in the attacks that are critical in ‘grounding’ an extension.

7. Summary and conclusion

We considered the problem of explaining the inner structure of complex extensions by reducing them to the grounded extension of an appropriate sub-framework. For that we analysed (minimal) *critical sets* of attacks, i. e., attacks that can be removed from a frame-

work in order to obtain equivalence of the given extension with the grounded extension. We also introduced the notion of *grounding distance* to quantitatively measure the effort required to ground extensions. Our main contribution is a comprehensive complexity analysis of certain decision problems wrt. six argumentation semantics.

For future work, we intend to investigate the potential of using the grounding distance in the context of *gradual evaluation* of argument strength [29,30,31], and in particular for relating sets of arguments wrt. their strength [11,12] as discussed at the end of Section 4. Moreover, following up on the work [6], another avenue for future work is to develop graphical tools for explaining argument acceptance through visualising the role of critical attacks and the grounding of extensions.

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